

@prefix rdf: <<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>> .
@prefix rdfs: <<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>> .
@prefix dcat: <<http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>> .
@prefix dcterms: <<http://purl.org/dc/terms/>> .
@prefix xsd: <<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>> .

:doore

 a dcat:Dataset ;
 dcterms:title "DOO-RE"@en ;
 dcterms:description "Ambient sensor dataset from a real-world meeting room."@en ;
 dcat:keyword "activity recognition"@en, "ambient sensor"@en, "public space"@en,
"IoT"@en, "time series"@en ;
 dcterms:creator "cdsn-lab" ;
 dcterms:issued "2023-11-14"^^xsd:date ;
 dcterms:modified "2024-02-21"^^xsd:date ;
 dcat:contactPoint <<http://cds.kaist.ac.kr/>> ;
 dcterms:spatial "Korea Institute of Advanced Science and Technology"@en ;
 dcterms:publisher "CDSN Lab @ KAIST"@en ;
 dcterms:license <<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>> ;
 dcat:distribution :doore-distribution ;
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:doore-distribution

 a dcat:Distribution ;
 dcterms:title "Download in CSV format" ;
 dcterms:description "Sensor dataset available for download in CSV format." ;
 dcat:downloadURL <<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.24558619>> ;
 dcterms:format "text/csv" ;
 dcat:mediaType "text/csv" ;
 dcterms:license <<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>> ;
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